

Soil Loss Estimation Using GIS and Remote Sensing Technique: A Case of Teaching and Research Farm, Kwara State University, Malete

Khadijat Oyebisi Alabi¹ ,
Kabir Adebayo¹

*1-Department of Crop Production, Faculty of Agriculture,
Kwara State University, Malete, Ilorin, Nigeria*

Corresponding Author: Khadijat Oyebisi Alabi

Received: 5 December 2023

e-mail: alabioyebisi@gmail.com

Accepted: 6 March 2024

Abstract

Due to ongoing cultivation, the Teaching and Research Farm of Kwara State University in Malete has seen quick and accelerated erosion. Run-off-related soil loss is a significant and persistent ecological problem in the study area. Information on soil loss is essential for promoting agricultural production and natural resource management. The average annual soil loss was calculated and mapped in this study using remote sensing and GIS. The soil loss was computed using the Revised Universal Soil Loss (RUSLE) Model. Using a topographic map at a scale of 1:50,000, an aster digital elevation model (DEM) with a spatial resolution of 20 m, a digital soil map at a scale of 1: 250,000, rainfall data spanning 39 years (1981-2020), and other data, RUSLE's soil loss variables were calculated. The RUSLE parameters were investigated and incorporated using a raster calculator in the geo-processing tools in the arc-GIS 10.1 environment to estimate and map the annual soil loss of the research region. The results show that the annual soil loss in the study region ranged from 48.553 to 1,476.606 t ha⁻¹ year⁻¹, cover around 100 ha of land. Most of the soil erosion affected areas are spatially situated in block 2B and 3A part of the farm. These are areas where low Ferric Luvisols and high Ferric Luvisols with higher soil erodibility character (21-33) values are dominant. Therefore, it was found that the main causes of soil erosion were slope gradient and length, followed by soil erodibility parameters. The study therefore recommended using sustainable soil and water conservation methods to address the problem of soil erosion in the study area.

Keywords: Soil Loss, Soil erodibility, Slope gradient, Arc-GIS, Ferric Luvisols, RUSLE

Introduction

During the process of soil erosion, topsoil on the soil surface is lifted off the ground by water or wind and transferred to other surfaces. It is regarded as the biggest environmental problem the world is currently facing, second only to population growth. According to Pimentel et al. (2009), who provided examples of the United States losing soil at a rate of 10-

40 times faster than the average replacement rate and China and India losing soil at a rate of 30-40 times faster, the majority of soil from farmlands is washed away about 10–40 times faster than it is being replaced. The trend of soil erosion increased during the 20th century. Soil erosion has reduced crop yield by 17%, the majority of which has happened since the end of World War II. It has been established in the literature that eroding soils emit harmful farm chemicals into streams, rivers, surface waters, and groundwater resources (N₂O), as well as atmospheric pollutants like carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide. Thirty percent of the world's arable land has become unusable during the past forty years due to erosion.

It is still difficult to find a model that can estimate soil loss from all sources of erosion from a particular site. One of the parametric models utilized to calculate soil erosion is the Universal Soil Loss Equation. Studies using the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE), Modified Universal Soil Loss Equation (MUSLE), Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE), Water Erosion Prediction Project (WEPP), Limberg Soil Erosion Model (LISEM), and Soil Loss Estimation Model for Southern Africa (SLEMSA) have shown that eroded soils carry harmful farm chemicals into streams and rivers and contaminate surface and groundwater resources. The USLE (Wischmeier and Smith 1978) was previously considered to be the best equation for calculating soil loss due to its simplicity and resilience. However, it has been demonstrated that when applied to areas of the world other than the United States of America, it is insufficient due to variations in the soil types and rainfall patterns found in these areas. In recent years, RUSLE has been used in several research across the globe (Adediji et al., 2010; Nangia et al., 2010; Sajaul et al., 2012).

This demonstrates the method's adaptability to locations with a range of climatic factors and soil types. The RUSLE erosion model, which was developed to calculate the average soil loss over the long term due to runoff from a certain field slope, would compute the average soil loss with the proper selection of its factor values. The soil loss predicted by RUSLE is brought on by sheet and rill erosion. Sheet erosion, the initial stage of water erosion, is the process by which rainfall and runoff remove a layer of soil from the surface of the land. Contrarily, rills are often located on agricultural land and are associated with agricultural activity.

There isn't much information available at the KWASU Teaching and Research Farm about soil loss or how likely soil erosion is to occur, and neither GIS nor remote sensing methods have been used to aid. Therefore, this work aims to estimate and map the geographical pattern of annual soil loss rate by water using the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) simulated using GIS and Remote sensing techniques.

Materials and Methods

The Teaching and Research Farm at Kwara State University in Malete (KWASU T&R), which is located in the Moro Local Government Area of Kwara State, served as the study's experimental location (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location Map of the study area. (Source - Alabi et al., 2017.)

It is located eight kilometers north of the agricultural buildings and covers about 100 hectares. The farm is located 360 meters above sea level, between Latitude $08^{\circ}71'N$ and Longitude $04^{\circ}44'E$, and the terrain is fairly gentle. It is situated in Nigeria's Southern Guinea Savannah ecological zone. It consists of a farm center and a space for teaching and research by the departments of crop production, agricultural economics, and extension services. It also includes a section for animal production, which includes fisheries and aquaculture, small and large ruminant, poultry, and rabbitry. It is characterized by distinctive wet and dry seasons with a mean annual rainfall of about 1150 mm, with a double maximal pattern between April and October. The dry season starts in November and lasts until March, whereas the wet season starts in April and concludes towards the end of October. The average yearly temperature ranges from 25 to $28.9^{\circ}C$ degrees. The land area is a part of the Nigerian basement complex's South-Western zone of basement reactivation. The area is predominantly used for the cultivation of arable crops such as maize, groundnut and cowpea, perennial trees such as cashew and mango. The site also contains a variety of grasses, including spear grass, elephant grass, and Guinea Gamba grass, as well as woody species including the baobab (*Adansonia digitata*), neem tree (*Azadractha indica*), and acacia (*acacia species*).

For this investigation, both primary and secondary data sources were used. Primary data were collected using GPS devices through field surveys, ground truth authentication, and observation. This gives precise information about what is happening in the study area. The six blocks that made up the farm were Crop Museum, Block 2A, Block 2B, Block 3A, Block 4, and Operation Feed Yourself field. To produce primary data pertaining to ground truth for the purpose of training the image utilizing supervised image classification and producing thematic land use and land cover maps, intensive field observations using GPS were conducted in each block of the farm. For each key land-use/cover category, ground control points (GCPs) were also acquired in order to validate accuracy. Additional data includes the soil map (1:250,000), the slope length-steepness (LS) factor, a 2019 Thematic Mapper (TM) multi-spectral image with a spatial resolution of 30 m (land-use/land-cover map), and 39 years (1981-2020) of rainfall records from the Lower Niger Basin. These data sources were all downloaded from the Global Land-cover Facility (www.landcover.org). The Google Earth image was also made and digitized. Each layer of the RUSLE parameters was discretized and structured to the DEM's (20×20) cell size in order to obtain a fine grid-based soil loss result and to derive a precise slope length-steepness factor value. Digital technology and the Google Earth image were used to produce a map of the research area's waterbodies. Published and unpublished resources, such as research papers, census reports, and journal articles that were gathered from various sources, as well as the aforementioned secondary data, were also used.

The Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) was used to calculate the mean yearly soil loss that took place in the Teaching and Research Farm using the enhanced LS factor estimation approach. The empirical formulation of the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) is:

$$A \text{ (M t/ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}) = R * K * LS * C * P \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 1}$$

where A is the mean annual soil loss (M t/ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹); R is the rainfall erosivity factor (MJ mm h⁻¹ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹); K is the soil erodibility factor (M t/ha⁻¹ MJ⁻¹ mm⁻¹); LS is the slope length–steepness factor (dimensionless); C is the cover and management factor (dimensionless); and P is the erosion support practice or land management factor (dimensionless and ranges from zero to one). The RUSLE model was simulated by GIS and Remote sensing techniques. While the raster calculator geo-processing tool, the R-value of each grid cell or block was determined from this continuous rainfall data.

$$R(\text{eq}) = -823.8 + 5.21Pr \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 2}$$

Where;

Req= Equivalent R factor for unique climatic condition\

Pr= annual precipitation, mm

Results and Discussion

Assessment of the rate of soil loss

In this work, the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model was used to calculate the mean annual soil loss rate ($t/ha^{-1} yr^{-1}$) cell by cell. The Teaching and Research Farm in Malete (Figure 1) also discovered and documented soil erosion danger zones. The following are a few of the raster maps that were made and discussed for each RUSLE parameter:

Rainfall erosivity (R) factor

According to Equation (2), the erosivity factor is estimated to be between 87.391 and 91.086 $MJ mm h^{-1} ha^{-1} yr^{-1}$. The rainfall erosivity factor, which also considers the amount and rate of runoff that is most likely to be associated with precipitation events, measures the influence of rainfall. The Lower Niger Basin Meteorological Station in Ilorin, Kwara State provided the mean annual rainfall for the research area, which was interpolated in the ArcGIS 10.1 environment using the inverse distance weighted approach (Table 1) to create unbroken rainfall data for each grid cell.

Figure 2. *Rainfall Erosivity (R) factor*

Soil erodibility (K) factor

The natural resistance of soil particles to the detaching and transporting power of precipitation is a sign of soil erodibility (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978). This component assesses a soil type's cohesiveness and resistance to dislodging and transport caused by the force of overland flow shear pressures and raindrop impacts. For a particular soil type, the K-factor is empirically computed to represent the physical and chemical properties of the soil that affect its erodibility potential (Figure 3). The Teaching and Research Farm's erodibility K-factor ranges from 10 to 33 $\text{mt/ha}^{-1} \text{MJ}^{-1} \text{mm}^{-1}$ (Table 1). The highest erodibility factor values were reported by Ozcan et al. (2008) using USLE and GIS, which is consistent with the findings of our work. Koulin et al. reported similar findings in the Chania watershed in Greece in 2009.

Table 1. Estimated K Value for Each Block

Block	Soil Name/Class	Estimated K value (metric tons $\text{ha}^{-1} \text{MJ}^{-1} \text{mm}^{-1}$)
Crop museum	High ferric Luvisols	21
2A	High to Medium ferric Luvisols	10 - 21
2B	High to Medium ferric Luvisols	10- 21
3A	Low ferric Luvisols	33
4	Low ferric Luvisols	33
Operation Yourself field	feed Medium ferric Luvisols	10

Figure 3. Soil Erodibility (K) factor

Slope length and steepness (LS) factor

Using Simms et al., (2003), the topographic component of RUSLE was calculated. Slope length was replaced for the upslope contributing area in order to account for the flow convergence and divergence in a three-dimensional complicated terrain situation. The (LS) factor, under otherwise identical conditions, is the ratio of soil loss per unit area from a field slope to that from a 22.13 m length of uniform 9% slope (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978). In this case, the slope-length (L sub-factor) refers to the distance between the beginning and end of the inter-rill process. The culmination occurs when the flow concentrates into a rill or other man-made channel, such as a terrace or diversion, or when the slope begins to drop and the subsequent depositional process begins (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978; Renard *et al.*, 1996).

Figure 4. Slope Length and Steepness (LS) Factor

Slope determination utilizing a geographic information system (GIS) has benefits for a wide range of environmental models because slope properties are typically needed as input for landslides, land planning and construction, and other environmental models (Dunn & Hickey, 1998). The length of the slope-drawbacks. When applying the Universal Soil Loss Equation, the cumulative uphill length from each cell can be used to overcome the limitations of slope-length computation by taking into consideration convergent flow pathways and depositional areas (Hickey, 2000). The supposed transport capacity of the flow is measured by the LS factor in the RUSLE (Moore & Wilson, 1992). Without accounting for the intricate three-dimensional geometry of the landscape. The supposed transport capacity of the flow is measured by the LS factor in the RUSLE (Moore & Wilson, 1992). The slope-length calculation approach employed in USLE and RUSLE was based on the notion that the longer the slope, the greater the soil loss (Robert & Hilborn, 2000). This was done without taking into account the complicated three-dimensional geometry of the terrain (Figure 4). The results of slope length indicate that the prolonged areas of steep slopes are susceptible to severe erosion. In the Turkish Kazan watershed, Erdogan et al. (2007) used USLE and GIS models

and reported similar, reliable results. Crop Museum and Operation Feed Yourself Field's topography favoured less erosion in general. This suggests that the land is seriously endangered, which affects its output. High correlation between steep slopes and poor surface cover within the farm was also reported by Kouli, 2009 in the Crete watershed.

Support practice (P) factor.

The erosion control practice factor (P-factor) is the ratio of soil loss caused by a certain support practice to losses comparable to those caused by upslope and downslope agriculture (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978). The generated P-factor map (Figure 5) is not used to comprehend the conservation practices being applied in the research region. The preventative measures that affect drainage patterns, runoff concentration, and runoff velocity and minimize the erosive power of rainfall and runoff are considered in this component. The classed land-use/land-cover and slope thematic map format was converted to vector format and the corresponding p values were added to each combination of land-use/land-cover and slope classes in order to build a raster map of the P factor.

Figure 5. Support Practice (P) Factor

Cover and management (C) factor.

The cover and management (C) factor is defined as the ratio of soil loss from land with a specific vegetation to the corresponding soil loss from a continuous fallow (Wischmeier & Smith, 1978; Morgan, 2005). It is the component that can be changed the most and is typically taken into consideration when developing a conservation strategy. The major method for gathering data on the dominant categories of land use and land cover in the study area was unsupervised categorization. On the basis of this data, supervised classification supported by GCPs was used to produce themed land-cover maps. The thematic land-use and land-cover raster map of Teaching and Research Farm, Maleta was then

transformed to vector format in order to assign the proper cover and management factor value derived from various studies. The result was a C-factor raster map, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Cover and Management(c) factor Map

The primary land-uses/covers of the Teaching and Research Farm that were identified using supervised image classification were water bodies and cultivated land. Maize, cowpeas, groundnuts, melon, guinea corn, and other vegetation dominated the area. Crop covers with the greatest C-factor values (0.1). This ensures that annual crops like millet and maize do not mitigate the direct effects of rainfall on soil resources, unlike forest land. Thus, the final map that shows the anticipated annual soil loss of the Teaching and Research farm was produced by superimposing the aforementioned five parameters (K, R, LS, C, and P) using Eq. (1), raster calculator geo-processing tools, and the ArcGIS10.1 environment (Figure 7).

The cell sizes for the DEM were resampled (20×20 m), and each layer was organized in a grid style. The soil erosion map of the study area was divided into six classes for the purpose of management prioritization, as shown in Table 1 and Figure 7. The level of soil loss risk in the research region has also been classified and the potential amount of soil loss has been predicted using the statistical approach. As shown in Figure 7, the annual soil loss of Teaching and Research farm extends from 0 to $1,476.606 \text{ M t/ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ with a mean annual soil loss rate of $47.4 \text{ Mt/ ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The total annual soil loss in the Teaching and Research farm is 1476.606 t; which covers about 100 ha of land. This lost is at a rate much greater than the tolerable soil loss rate (Table 2).

Table 2. Annual Soil loss range, Block coverage and severity class

Annual soil loss (tone)	Soil erosion risk class	Block coverage	Percent of total soil loss
0-48.553	Low	Crop museum	2.02
48.553-140.031	Moderate	Operation feed yourself field	5.83
140.031- 280.367	High	2A and 2B	11.68
280.367- 455.398	Very high	4	18.97
455.398-1476.606	Severe	3A	61.5

Figure 7. Soil loss rate Map

Tolerable soil loss rate (FAO, 1984) is defined as the highest allowable soil loss rate that can support economic growth and high levels of production. Since the majority of the primary soil types on the Teaching and Research Farms in Malete have soil depths between 0 and 150 meters, the FAO's (1994) tolerable soil loss rate for deep and very deep soil depths is 4.2 to 7.2 t/ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. This suggests that the land is seriously endangered, which affects its output. This implies that the land is gravely in jeopardy, which has an impact on its productivity. Additionally, the system that keeps life from dying could deteriorate until it reaches an irreversible condition. The Teaching and Research farm's yearly soil loss ranges from 0 to 1,476.606 Mt/ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, with a mean rate of 47.4 metric t/ ha⁻¹ year⁻¹. In the Teaching and Research farm, the total yearly soil loss is 1476.606 t, which occupies a space of around 100 ha. Compared to the permitted rate of soil loss, this loss is occurring far more quickly than the allowable rate of soil loss (Table 2). Tolerable soil loss rate (FAO, 1984) is defined as the highest allowable soil loss rate that can support economic growth and high levels of production. Since, most of the major soil types of Teaching and Research farm, Malete have soil depth ranges from 0 – 150 m deep (Alabi et al., 2017), the soil loss rate in the study area is far beyond FAO (1994) tolerable soil loss rate of 4.2–7.2 t/ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ for deep and very deep soil depth respectively. Kumar et al., (2022) reported an average annual soil loss of 1.60 t. ha⁻¹. yr⁻¹ in the lower Chambal basin in Madhya Pradesh using RUSLE model. Adhikary et al., (2014), Suryawanshi et al., (2023) reported similar results by comparing USLE and RUSLE models in Central Indian Chambal River Basin.

Conclusion

Information about the quantitative and spatial extent of soil loss derived by modeling of RUSLE parameters Malete ensures the management of spatially variable data and inaccessible location where ground-based observation is challenging by using GIS and Remote sensing techniques in Teaching and Research farm. As a result, the method can be used in other areas of the community for the evaluation and identification of regions that are

prone to erosion, the setting of conservation priorities, and the evaluation of the effectiveness of different land management strategies.

The results of this study take into account the erosion risk map and the spatially distributed soil loss rate of Kwara State University's Teaching and Research Farm in Malete. The annual soil loss at Malete's Teaching and Research farm ranges from 0 to 1476.606 metric tons. Slope-length and gradient (LS) factor was shown to be the most important RUSLE parameter by the results as well. According to the soil erodibility (K) factor, the potential soil loss is therefore frequently greater along the steeper slope and in areas with less vegetation cover.

The areas used for Operation Feed Yourself and Crop Museum Block have been discovered to be the least prone to soil erosion. Therefore, in order to reduce soil erosion, the research area's conservation and management measures are strongly suggested. Areas where significant soil loss was detected should be given careful thought. An appropriate land use plan and an Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) are required for the locations that have been made accessible on the University's Teaching and Research farm. For immediate soil protection efforts in their agricultural regions, local residents and researchers in the area should embrace various soil protection approaches, such as mulching, contour plowing, repeated cropping, and other indigenous soil conservation strategies. Additionally, using enough vegetative cover and adding organic manure should be considered.

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